

To Study Thyroid Profile as Risk Factor in Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) Patients

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Abstract:

Aims: To study the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction as risk factor associated with severity of NAFLD.

Objectives: Primary Objective: To assess prevalence of hypothyroidism in NAFLD patients.

Secondary objective: To assess association of hypothyroidism as risk factor in NAFLD patients.

Methodology: Present study was an observational prospective study between January 2023 to June 2024 in patients between age group 25-65 years attend OPD/IPD services at Department of Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur.

Results: The study observed significant associations between thyroid function parameters and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), particularly with thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free triiodothyronine (fT3), and free thyroxine (fT4) levels. Lower levels of fT3 and fT4 were found to be associated with increased odds of NAFLD ($p < 0.001$). Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in regulating hepatic lipid metabolism. They modulate the expression of genes involved in lipogenesis, β -oxidation, and cholesterol metabolism in the liver. Reduced thyroid hormone levels, as observed in hypothyroidism or subclinical hypothyroidism, can lead to impaired lipid metabolism, promoting hepatic steatosis.

Conclusion: Thyroid hormones influence insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism, with hypothyroidism often associated with insulin resistance and dysglycemia. Insulin resistance is a key pathogenic factor in NAFLD development, contributing to excessive hepatic lipid accumulation. Thus, alterations in thyroid function may exacerbate insulin resistance and further predispose individuals to NAFLD (36). Thyroid hormones exert anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic effects in various tissues, including the liver. Hypothyroidism is associated with increased pro-inflammatory cytokine levels and oxidative stress, which can promote hepatic inflammation and fibrogenesis, contributing to NAFLD progression.

Keywords: NAFLD, TSH, T3, T4.

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Introduction

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is defined as a condition where more than 5% of the body's hepatic cells contain fatty deposits without a history of alcohol consumption. This deposition of fat can cause a variety of diseases ranging from simple steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), cirrhosis, liver failure, and hepatocellular carcinoma [1].

The frequency of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) has increased significantly throughout the past periods, and it has become the prominent reason of liver disease worldwide with a global prevalence of one billion, which can be moderately recognized to the rising prevalence of obesity. The global prevalence of NAFLD is 24%, with the highest rates are reported from South America, the Middle East, and Asia.

NAFLD is diagnosed when daily alcohol consumption is ≤ 20 g/day in women and ≤ 30 g/day in men and other causes of the disease have been excluded (autoimmune, viral, steatogenic drugs, etc.) [2-3]. Recent studies show that NAFLD can be seen in both weak and obese populations [4]. According to epidemiological studies, 30% of the general population has steatosis, 5% of whom develop NASH [1]. NAFLD is considered to be associated with the expression of multi-metabolic disorders [5]. NAFLD is associated with multiple factors such as hypertension, insulin resistance, diabetes, dyslipidemia, obesity, and hyperuricemia [2,6-8].

Endocrine hormones are generally involved in cell metabolism, regulation of energy expenditure and fat distribution in the human body and thereby play an important role in the development of metabolic abnormalities. The thyroid gland is significantly involved in energy homeostasis, lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, regulation of body weight and adipogenesis [9,10]. In a clinical setting, subclinical hypothyroidism has been associated with metabolic syndrome, cardiovascular mortality and disturbance of lipid metabolism [11,12]. In recent years, growing body of evidence has led to speculation on the association between NAFLD/NASH and thyroid dysfunction.

NAFLD/NASH is supposed to be a hepatic feature of metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance [13,14]. Hypothyroidism has been reported to be associated with obesity and metabolic syndrome [15-17]. Insulin resistance in the context of hypothyroidism and its alleviation with treatment of the hypothyroidism has been reported [18].

Hypothyroidism was more prevalent in patients with type 2 diabetes and in some reports was associated with diabetic microangiopathy [19,20]. Associations of hypothyroidism with these metabolic

abnormalities, which are frequently accompanied by NAFLD/NASH, strengthen the notion of association between hypothyroidism and NAFLD/NASH. While the underlying pathophysiology for this association is still not clear, several mechanisms have been proposed.

Uric acid (UA) is a natural end product of purine metabolism. UA levels being elevated due to factors that cause NAFLD, hyperuricemia itself is a proven cause of NAFLD, independent of obesity or insulin resistance [30].

Material and Methods:

Type of Study: Hospital based Observational Prospective study.

Study Population: All patients age between 25 to 65 years attended OPD/IPD services at Department of Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur from January 2023 to June 2024.

Place of Study: Department of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur

Duration of Study: 18 months from approval of IEC [January 2023 to June 2024]

Detailed history and necessary investigations will be undertaken. The purpose of the study will be explained to the patient and informed consent obtained.

Patients are selected for study that satisfies all inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Institute Ethics Committee approval will be taken before undertaking the study.

Written and informed consent will be taken from all participants before enrolment into the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- The diagnosis of NAFLD will be based on meeting the following criteria: non-alcoholic, fatty degeneration detected by imaging or histological examination with other liver diseases excluded, noninvasive assessment for significant fibrosis which is FIB-4 grading.
- Grading: FIB-4.
- 0.00 - 1.29 low risk for advanced liver fibrosis.
- 1.30-2.67 intermediate risk.
- > 2.67 high risk.
- Age = 25 years and < 65 years of both genders will be studied.

Exclusion Subjects:

- Alcoholics.
- Patients with renal disease.
- Patients on Drugs modifying CIMT (ACE inhibitors, statins, aspirin & ARB).

- Those not willing to give informed consent

Criteria for NAFLD Diagnosis

- AST/ALT ratio >1.0
- APRI >1.5.
- FIB-4 >2.67.
- NAFLD fibrosis score >0.675.

Hypothyroidism: Primary hypothyroidism is defined by TSH concentrations above the reference range (most commonly used 0–4–4–0 mIU/L) and free thyroxine concentrations below the reference range, which is dependent on the type of assay used and the population studied (figure 1).

Figure 1:

Methodology

Present study was an observational prospective study between January 2023 to June 2024 in patients between age group 25-65 years attend OPD/IPD services at Department of Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur. Data will be collected using a pretested pro forma meeting the objectives of the study. Demographic and anthropometric data will be obtained (age, gender, weight, height, and body mass index (BMI)) and serum biochemistry was assessed including total cholesterol, triglyceride, alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), gamma glutamyl transferase (GGT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), total bilirubin, albumin and thyroid profile (TSH, free T4). All biochemical parameters will be received after 8 hours of angle and were measured on a multichannel autoanalyzer.

Aim of study

To study the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction as risk factors associated with severity of NAFLD.

Objective

Primary Objective: To assess prevalence of hypothyroidism in NAFLD patients.

Secondary Objective: To assess association of hypothyroidism as risk factors in NAFLD patients.

Observations

The investigation into thyroid function parameters within this study provides crucial insights into the endocrine health status of the examined population, focusing on thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free triiodothyronine (fT3), and free thyroxine (fT4) levels.

The mean TSH concentration is determined to be 1.82 mIU/l, with a standard deviation of 1.3 mIU/l, indicating the average level of this hormone responsible for regulating thyroid activity. Meanwhile, the mean fT3 concentration is recorded at 2.62 pg/ml, with a standard deviation of 0.5 pg/ml, and the mean fT4 concentration is 2.15 ng/dl, with a standard deviation of 1.9 ng/dl.

Table 1: prevalence hypothyroidism in study population

Hypothyroidism [N (%)]	Frequency	Percentage
	49	15.3

In the investigated population, hypothyroidism exhibited an incidence rate of 15.3%, with 49 individuals identified as having this thyroid disorder.

Table 2: Comparison & association of Thyroid profile in Non-NAFLD and NAFLS study population

Thyroid Function Test	Non-NAFLD(N=160)	NAFLD(N=160)	p-Value
TSH (mIU/l)	1.98 ±1.4	1.67 ±1.1	0.028
ft3 (pg/ml)	2.51 ±0.3	2.68 ±0.8	< 0.001
ft4 (ng/dl)	2.3 ±0.8	2.10 ±1.9	< 0.001

In this comparative analysis of thyroid function tests between individuals with and without non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), significant differences were observed in the levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free triiodothyronine (ft3), and free thyroxine (ft4). Among the 160 participants without NAFLD, the mean TSH level was 1.98 mIU/l with a standard deviation of 1.4 mIU/l, while among the 160 participants diagnosed with NAFLD, the mean TSH level was slightly lower at 1.67 mIU/l with a standard deviation of 1.1 mIU/l. Statistical analysis revealed a significant p-value of 0.028 for TSH levels between the two groups, suggesting a potential association between TSH levels and the presence of NAFLD.

Similarly, for ft3 levels, significant differences were observed. Among individuals without NAFLD, the mean ft3 level was 2.51 pg/ml with a standard deviation of 0.3 pg/ml, whereas among those with NAFLD, the mean ft3 level was slightly higher at 2.68 pg/ml with a standard deviation of 0.8 pg/ml. Statistical analysis revealed a highly significant p-value of less than 0.001 for ft3 levels between the two groups.

Additionally, for ft4 levels, significant differences were also noted. Among individuals without NAFLD, the mean ft4 level was 2.3 ng/dl with a standard deviation of 0.8 ng/dl, while among those with NAFLD, the mean ft4 level was slightly lower at 2.10 ng/dl with a standard deviation of 1.9 ng/dl. Statistical analysis revealed a highly significant p-value of less than 0.001 for ft4 levels between the two groups.

Regarding thyroid function tests, free triiodothyronine (ft3) (OR: 0.943, 95% CI: 0.867-0.992) and free thyroxine (ft4) (OR: 0.951, 95% CI: 0.931-0.969) demonstrated negative associations with NAFLD, suggesting that lower levels of these hormones were associated with increased odds of NAFLD. Thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) also showed a significant association with NAFLD (OR: 0.993, 95% CI: 0.962-1.002), albeit with a smaller effect size.

Discussion

The study revealed a notable gender disparity in the prevalence of NAFLD, with a significantly higher proportion of males diagnosed with the condition compared to females ($p < 0.001$). This finding aligns with existing literature indicating that males are more predisposed to NAFLD, possibly due to

differences in hormonal regulation, fat distribution, and lifestyle factors (31-32).

The observed gender disparity underscores the importance of considering gender-specific risk factors and interventions in the management of NAFLD. Thyroid function analysis showed mean TSH levels of 1.82 ± 1.3 mIU/L, mean ft3 of 2.62 ± 0.5 pg/mL, and mean ft4 of 2.15 ± 1.9 ng/dL. These findings are within normal ranges, yet the slightly lower TSH levels in NAFLD patients may reflect a subtle hypothyroid state, which has been linked to metabolic syndrome and NAFLD (Pagadala et al., 2012)[33]. The study observed significant associations between thyroid function parameters and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), particularly with thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free triiodothyronine (ft3), and free thyroxine (ft4) levels. Lower levels of ft3 and ft4 were found to be associated with increased odds of NAFLD ($p < 0.001$).

Thyroid hormones play a crucial role in regulating hepatic lipid metabolism. They modulate the expression of genes involved in lipogenesis, β -oxidation, and cholesterol metabolism in the liver. Reduced thyroid hormone levels, as observed in hypothyroidism or subclinical hypothyroidism, can lead to impaired lipid metabolism, promoting hepatic steatosis (34).

Conclusion

Thyroid hormones influence insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism, with hypothyroidism often associated with insulin resistance and dysglycemia. Insulin resistance is a key pathogenic factor in NAFLD development, contributing to excessive hepatic lipid accumulation.

Thus, alterations in thyroid function may exacerbate insulin resistance and further predispose individuals to NAFLD (36). Thyroid hormones exert anti-inflammatory and antifibrotic effects in various tissues, including the liver. Hypothyroidism is associated with increased pro-inflammatory cytokine levels and oxidative stress, which can promote hepatic inflammation and fibrogenesis, contributing to NAFLD progression (35).

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